

FORMATION OF IMMUNITY AGAINST MARGINAL CULTURE IN STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract This article discusses the need for students, especially girls, to strengthen their position in society by paying more attention to social and political activity in every field, to find their place not only in society, but also in self-education in various aspects of life, and In the process of developing self-awareness, it is reflected how important it is to form immunity against marginal culture.

Key words: gender approach, marginal culture, immunity, research,

It should be noted that the main factor for raising the status of the young generation, especially women, increasing their social and political activity, and ensuring their activity in the reforms implemented in our country is the combination of education and personnel training. In this regard, all conditions are created for students to get high-level education, and special opportunities are created for our girls to get education.

Today, full participation of women in the science and education system, active participation in the country's economic development, state security, domestic and foreign policy issues is becoming a commonplace. Depending on the participation of women and girls in the economic and political processes, their support from the society, it is possible to determine the level of progress and development of the country. For this purpose, we can ensure their socio-pedagogical preparation by developing self-awareness of future teachers, especially our female students. Only a future teacher who has the skills of gender self-awareness can implement a gender approach in the educational process and in the future of our young women and girls, not only in our country, but also in the world education system. it is important to ensure that they achieve significant gains without losing their identity when faced with a marginalized culture in the learning process. First of all, we need to know what kind of culture is a marginal culture that is alien to us. Marganal culture is the lowest level of culture, and the people belonging to this culture are a group of people who have not sufficiently adapted to the environment, have not been able to establish a sufficient relationship with the new cultural environment, and have narrow spiritual interests. Marginal culture is characterized by the vagueness and

abstraction of socio-cultural norms and directions. Difficult to solve problems, which are basic for a person, make it difficult to acquire new values, social status. The socio-cultural life of such individuals is characterized by instability. Such people face difficulties and pressures in carrying out their activities. They are unable to conduct their relationships with others thoughtfully and adhere to cultural norms of a positive nature. Students from different regions of our Republic often come to such an environment. Such a person tries to maintain the opportunity between two cultures necessary for his future cultural development. However, self-doubt, psychological pressure, and alienation are the basis for exposure to a marginalized culture. As a result, a person falls into a comfortable but closed environment. This environment often causes them to feel hopeless and depressed, which limits the socio-cultural outlook of young people and their ability to communicate widely with members of society.

In order to make students immune to marginal culture, we need to arm them with legal knowledge, positive views, healthy religious beliefs, and the basics of national cultural outlook. In this regard, the importance of national pride, universal and national values, traditions specific to our national culture, and examples of leading culture is required in the society of Uzbekistan. In addition, punishing them without depriving them of their freedom and explaining the negative consequences of their actions will also make it possible to achieve efficiency in this regard. It is necessary to regularly conduct educational work with students who are inclined to marginal culture. To do this, professors and teachers are required to determine the marginal culture, national cultural worldview, life beliefs, values and cultural models of each student, comprehensively analyze their activities, rely on the results achieved in the implementation of pedagogical activities. As we noted above, the marginalized are mainly students, teenagers and unorganized youth. Marginalization of students reduces their level of socialization and has a negative effect on their activation. As a result, students' self-expression directions are limited. Moreover, they lack socio-cultural mechanisms and legal knowledge. Students' ignorance of legal norms is the basis of negative behavior related to breaking the law. As a result, the position and role of law enforcement officers and the state in the field of human rights protection will decrease. As a result, they show negative qualities such as deviant behavior and negative self-expression: drunkenness, theft, vandalism, crime, drunkenness, national intolerance.

In order to find a solution to the problem of marginalization in society, it is necessary to improve the scientific-methodological support of educational

processes and implement the mechanisms of strengthening state control. For this, first of all, it is necessary to stabilize the life of society, expand the scale of the cultural environment, and create a healthy cultural environment for pupils and students. It is also necessary to interest them in learning, to develop creative and critical thinking, to activate cooperative actions, to ensure stability and calmness, and to discover systematically functioning structures. In the fight against marginalization, there is a growing need to identify pedagogical and psychological factors affecting marginalized groups, develop new methods, and analyze specific levels of this phenomenon.

Therefore, it has a special place in the education of a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, which has left a name in our country with its unique talent, deep knowledge, level and ingenuity, and has an independent worldview and philosophical observation. Today, among hundreds of doctors of science and academicians, thousands of candidates of science, our women and girls who are diligently serving the development of our country with their knowledge and talent are increasing significantly. In order to further increase the ranks of such talented people, we must all work together so that our youth, especially our female students, do not fall under the influence of marginal culture. One of the main tasks of today is to educate our youth so that they have not lost their intelligence and have spiritual and scientific knowledge.

In order to attract women to science in every country, to provide comprehensive support and encouragement to new ideas and developments of women engaged in science education and scientific activities in various sectors of the economy, the state of scientific activity programs have been developed. This encourages young people to create more enterprising, practical and innovative projects. In conclusion, the formation of a sense of self-awareness based on a gender approach in students, mainly in our girls, is not only a matter of justice and education, but also a matter of supporting innovation, developing society, and realizing our potential. We can create a fairer and more prosperous society for future generations by expanding girls' educational opportunities, removing obstacles to higher education and scientific research, and increasing their role. The more educated, self-aware women among our students, the more we support them, the more prosperous our country will be, this will serve as a solid foundation for a bright future.

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